

Synthesis of 2'-aryl-3- N^{10} -[(acetylamino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones] and 5'-arylidine-2-aryl-3- N^{10} -[(acetylamino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones] and their antimicrobial and diuretic activities

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Abstract : Thirty-nine new phenothiazino-4-oxo-thiazolidines and their 5-arylidines were synthesized and evaluated for their antimicrobial and diuretic activity. The structure of all the products was corroborated by IR, ^1H NMR, mass spectra and elemental analysis. Some of the newly synthesized compounds show promising antimicrobial and diuretic activity.

Keywords : Synthesis, antimicrobial, diuretic, thiazolidino-arylidines.

Introduction

4-Oxothiazolidine derivatives are known to possess broad spectrum of biological activities such as antifungal, hypnotic, antibacterial, antiviral, anthelmintic, diuretic, antihistaminic and analgesic¹⁻⁸. Phenothiazine has been also shown to possess various pharmacological properties. Heterocyclic variation at 10th position of phenothiazine nucleus remarkably increase its pharmacological activities⁸⁻¹⁰. Thiazolidinone posses potent biological activity and built in ($\text{O}=\text{C}-\text{N}-\text{C}-\text{S}$) as a toxophoric unit. Thus it was thought worthwhile to synthesize some new N^{10} -[(substituted arylidene hydrazino)-acetyl]-10H-phenothiazine, 2-substituted aryl-3- N^{10} -[(acetylamino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones]-10H-phenothiazine and 5-arylidine-2-substituted aryl-3- N^{10} -[(acetylamino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones]-10H-phenothiazine as per Scheme 1. These compounds were evaluated for their antimicrobial and diuretic activities.

Results and discussion

Phenothiazine on substitution by chloroacetyl chloride gave N^{10} -chloroacetyl-10H-phenothiazine 1. The compound 1 on amination with hydrazine hydrate afforded

N^{10} -(hydrazino acetyl)-10H-phenothiazine 2. The compound 2 on condensation with various substituted aromatic carbonyls yielded N^{10} -[(substituted arylidene hydrazino)acetyl]-10H-phenothiazines 3. The compound 3 on condensation with thioglycolic acid yielded 2-substituted aryl-3- N^{10} -[(acetyl amino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones]-10H-phenothiazines 4. The compound 4 on further reaction with various selected carbonyls in the presence of sodium ethoxide yielded 5-arylidine-2-substituted aryl-3- N^{10} -[(acetyl amino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones]-10H-phenothiazines 5 (Table 1). The structural confirmation of the products were recognized by their elemental analysis, IR, ^1H NMR and mass spectral data.

The compounds 3a-m, 4a-m and 5a-m were screened for their antibacterial activity against *Klebsilla penumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Streptococcus aureus* and *Shigella dysenteriae* at 25 and 50 ppm concentrations and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Crysosporium pannical*, *Rizopus oryzae* and *Candida albicans* at 100 and 500 ppm concentrations by filter paper disc method^{11,12}. Standard antibacterial Streptomycin and antifungals Griseofulvin and Diethane M-45 were also tested under similar conditions for comparison. The synthesized

Compd.	R	R ¹
3,4,5a	H	-C ₆ H ₅
3,4,5b	CH ₃	2-ClC ₆ H ₄
3,4,5c	CH ₃	3-ClC ₆ H ₄
3,4,5d	CH ₃	4-ClC ₆ H ₄
3,4,5e	CH ₃	2-BrC ₆ H ₄
3,4,5f	CH ₃	3-BrC ₆ H ₄
3,4,5g	CH ₃	4-BrC ₆ H ₄
3,4,5h	H	2-OHC ₆ H ₄
3,4,5i	H	3-OHC ₆ H ₄
3,4,5j	H	4-OHC ₆ H ₄
3,4,5k	H	2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄
3,4,5l	H	3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄
3,4,5m	H	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) ClCOCH₂Cl, (ii) NH₂NH₂·H₂O (98%), (iii) RCOR¹, (iv) HSCH₂COOH, (v) C₂H₅ONa/RCOR¹

compounds **3e**, **3f**, **3g**, **4e**, **4f**, **4g**, **5e**, **5f** and **5g** showed a promising antibacterial activity while the compounds **3e**, **3f**, **4f**, **4g**, **5d**, **5e**, **5f** and **5g** disclosed highest antifungal activity. Amongst the compounds tested for antimicrobial activity, compounds possessing halogens particularly bromine showed the highest activity against the standards Streptomycin (for antibacterial) and Griseofulvin and Diethane M-45 (for antifungal). Results are reported in the Tables 2 and 3 respectively.

Diuretic activity of the synthesized compounds **3a-m**, **4a-m** and **5a-m** was evaluated by Lipschitz method¹³ in adult male rats, fasted overnight with free access to water loaded orally with 5 mL/100 in bw normal saline. All the test compounds 50 mg/kg (oral) and standard drug furosemide at a dose of 30 mg/kg (oral), suspended in 0.5% gum acacia and administered to the animals of respective groups in a volume of 5 ml/100 g. One group of animals was taken as a control. All animals were used once in a week. The urine flow was in order of 1 ml/h/rat. Diuretic activity results revealed that compounds **3c** and **4c** (42.67 and 39.09) showed significant activity whereas other compounds **3b**, **3e**, **4a**, **4b**, **4g**, **5b**, **5d**, **5f** and **5g** (33.90, 36.87, 32.57, 31.36, 32.15, 32.92, 36.17, 32.53 and 33.63) exhibited moderate diuretic activity. Results reported in the Table 4 clearly showed that 3-chloro derivatives of 4-oxo thiazolidine ring markedly increase the diuretic potency amongst the tested compounds.

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu 8201 PC FTIR (ν_{\max} in cm⁻¹), ¹H NMR spectra on a Bruker DRX-300 spectrophotometer in CDCl₃ at 200 MHz using TMS as an internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on Zeol SX-102 spectrometer. The purity of the compound was checked by TLC using silica gel-G coated plates.

*N*¹⁰-Chloroacetyl-10H-phenothiazine (1) :

The equimolar solution of phenothiazine (0.1 M) and chloroacetyl chloride (0.1 M) in methanol (50 mL) with triethyl amine (10.0 M) was refluxed on a steam bath for about 10 h. The methanol was removed under reduced pressure and the solid thus obtained was dried and re-

Note

Table 1. Physical and spectral data of the compounds 3b-m, 4b-m and 5b-m

Compd.	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	IR (ν_{\max} cm^{-1}) principal peaks	^1H NMR (δ)
3b	134	76	2930, 1485 and 1370 (-C-CH ₃), 1548 (-N=C<), 765 (C-Cl)	1.10 (3H, s, N=C-CH ₃), 4.35 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 6.90-7.95 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.76 (1H, s, NH)
3e	138	68	2928, 1482 and 1365 (-C-CH ₃), 1545 (-N=C<), 612 (C-Br)	1.16 (3H, s, N=C-CH ₃), 4.34 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 6.95-7.90 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.78 (1H, s, NH)
3h	161	56	1585 (-N=CH-), 3320 (hydroxyl)	4.35 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 4.88 (1H, s, N=CH), 6.91-8.00 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.74 (1H, s, NH)
3m	160	59	1588 (-N=CH-), 2930 (CH ₃)	1.58 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 4.35 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 4.80 (1H, s, N=CH), 7.12-8.12 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.76 (1H, s, NH)
4b	167	71	1719 (>C=O, cyclic), 658 (C-S-C), 765 (C-Cl)	1.11 (3H, s, N-C-CH ₃), 3.68 (2H, s, -CH ₂ -S), 4.35 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 7.16-8.10 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.75 (1H, s, NH)
4e	173	73	1722 (>C=O, cyclic), 652 (C-S-C), 609 (C-Br)	1.12 (3H, s, N-C-CH ₃), 3.65 (2H, s, -CH ₂ -S), 4.32 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 7.09-8.05 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.78 (1H, s, NH)
4h	215	62	1719 (>C=O, cyclic), 652 (C-S-C), 3325 (hydroxyl)	3.13 (1H, s, N-CH), 3.56 (2H, s, -CH ₂ -S), 4.40 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 7.18-8.11 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.77 (1H, s, NH)
4i	200	58	1719 (>C=O, cyclic), 653 (C-S-C), 3315 (hydroxyl)	3.15 (1H, s, N-CH), 3.55 (2H, s, -CH ₂ -S), 4.39 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 7.10-8.10 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.76 (1H, s, NH)
4m	155	61	1722 (>C=O, cyclic), 658 (C-S-C), 2932 (CH ₃)	1.18 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 3.15 (1H, s, N-CH), 3.55 (2H, s, -CH ₂ -S), 4.38 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 7.12-8.16 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.78 (1H, s, NH)

Table-1 (contd.)

5b	163	71	1625 (>C=C<), 2938 (C-CH ₃), 710 (C-Cl)	1.16 (3H, s, N-C-CH ₃), 1.65 (3H, s, C=C-CH ₃), 4.35 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 7.18-8.17 (16H, m, Ar-H), 7.73 (1H, s, NH)
5e	173	66	1624 (>C=C<), 2932 (C-CH ₃), 610 (C-Br)	1.12 (3H, s, N-C-CH ₃), 1.66 (3H, s, C=C-CH ₃), 4.36 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 7.15-8.20 (16H, m, Ar-H), 7.64 (1H, s, NH)
5h	173	60	1622 (>C=CH-Ar), 3335 (hydroxyl)	3.20 (1H, s, N-CH), 4.35 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 5.16 (1H, s, C=CH-Ar), 7.11-8.19 (16H, m, Ar-H), 7.74 (1H, s, NH)
5m	207	62	1619 (>C=CH-Ar), 2938 (C-CH ₃)	1.15 (6H, s, 2 × Ar-CH ₃), 4.44 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 5.18 (1H, s, C=CH-Ar), 7.11-8.14 (16H, m, Ar-H), 7.78 (1H, s, NH)

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of the compounds 3a-m, 4a-m and 5a-m

Compd.	<i>K. pneumoniae</i> (ppm)		<i>E. coli</i> (ppm)		<i>S. dysenteriae</i> (ppm)		<i>S. aureus</i> (ppm)	
	25	50	25	50	25	50	25	50
3e	+++	++++	+++	+++	++	+++	+++	+++
3f	++	++++	+++	+++	++	+++	++	+++
3g	++	+++	++	+++	+++	++++	+++	+++
4e	+++	+++	++	++	+++	+++	++	+++
4f	++	+++	++	+++	+++	++++	+++	+++
4g	+++	+++	+++	+++	+	++	++	++
5e	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++	+++
5f	+++	++++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
5g	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
SM	+++	++++	+++	++++	+++	++++	++++	++++

SM = Streptomycin, inhibition diameter in mm :- (-) <7; (+) 8-10; (++) 10-16; (+++) 16-23; (++++) 23-28.

crystallized from ethanol to get compound 1, yield 70%, m.p. 145-146 °C (Found : N, 4.58; C, 59.21; H, 3.01. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₀OSNCl : N, 5.08; C, 60.98; H, 3.62%); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3035, 1575, 1550, 1475, 870, 735 (phenothiazine nucleus), 2888 (-CH₂) and 2275, 2240, 1792 (>N-C=O), 768 (C-Cl) and 692 (C-S-C); ¹H NMR : δ 4.40 (2H, s, -CH₂) and 6.65-7.42 (8H, m, Ar-H); MS : 275 (M⁺), 246, 226, 77.

*N*¹⁰-(Hydrazino acetyl)-10H-phenothiazine (2) :

Compound 1 (0.08 M) and hydrazine hydrate (0.08 M) in methanol (40 mL) was refluxed on a steam bath for about 12 h. It was then cooled and filtered to get a product which was recrystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture to give compound 2, yield 80%, m.p. 165-167 °C (Found : N, 15.04; C, 61.43; H, 4.23. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₃OSN₃ : N, 15.49; C, 61.99; H, 4.79%); IR

Note

Table 3. Antifungal activity of the compounds 3a-m, 4a-m and 5a-m

Compd.	<i>A. niger</i> (ppm)		<i>C. pannical</i> (ppm)		<i>R. oryzae</i> (ppm)		<i>C. albicans</i> (ppm)	
	100	500	100	500	100	500	100	500
3e	++	+++	-	+	+	++	+	++
3f	+	++	++	+++	++	+++	+	+
4f	++	+++	++	+++	+	++	++	++
4g	+	++	++	+++	+	++	++	++
5d	-	++	++	-	+	-	+++	+++
5e	+	++	++	++	++	+++	++	++
5f	++	+++	+++	++	++	+++	++	+++
5g	++	+++	+++	+	++	+++	++	+++
GF	+++	++++	+++	++++	+++	++++	++++	++++
DM	+++	++++	+++	++++	+++	+++	+++	+++

GF = Griseofulvin : DM-Dithane M-45, inhibition diameter in mm : (-) 4-8; (+) 8-12; (++) 12-16; (+++) 16-23; (++++) 23-29.

Table 4. Diuretic activity of the compounds 3a-m, 4a-m and 5a-m

Compd.	Normal saline	Urine output	% Output	Diuretic
	loaded 5 ml/100 g b.w	(ML)		activity
3a	45.23	6.99	15.45	23.46
3b	46.63	10.41	22.32	33.90
3c	47.00	13.21	28.10	42.67
3d	46.42	7.83	16.86	25.56
3e	47.02	11.42	24.28	36.87
3f	46.54	6.46	13.88	21.08
3g	45.89	8.93	19.45	29.54
3h	47.47	8.46	17.82	27.06
3i	48.02	7.14	14.86	22.56
3j	47.21	6.99	14.80	22.47
3k	47.40	8.39	17.75	27.06
3l	46.66	8.14	17.44	26.48
3m	47.31	7.21	15.29	23.22
4a	47.27	10.14	21.45	32.57
4b	48.08	9.93	20.65	31.36
4c	45.41	11.69	25.74	39.09
4d	46.35	7.08	15.27	23.19
4e	45.32	7.21	15.90	24.14
4f	46.74	8.68	18.57	28.20
4g	46.74	9.39	21.17	32.15
4h	44.35	8.35	17.98	27.30
4i	46.42	6.39	13.84	21.02
4j	46.14	7.57	16.04	24.36
4k	14.17	7.57	17.79	27.02
4l	46.87	8.34	17.79	27.02
4m	46.72	7.22	15.45	23.46
5a	45.39	7.32	16.12	24.48
5b	45.71	6.31	13.80	20.95
5c	47.23	10.24	21.68	32.92

Table-4 (contd.)

5c	46.32	7.83	16.90	25.66
5d	47.18	11.24	23.82	36.17
5e	44.34	8.40	18.94	28.76
5f	45.42	9.73	21.42	32.53
5g	46.16	10.22	22.15	33.63
5h	46.35	7.08	15.27	23.19
5i	45.32	7.21	15.90	24.14
5j	46.74	8.68	18.57	28.20
5k	45.71	6.31	13.80	20.95
5l	44.34	8.40	18.94	28.76
5m	46.72	8.66	18.35	28.18
Furosemide	46.32	30.50	65.84	-
Control	46.48	7.14	15.36	-

(cm^{-1}): 3415, 3335 and 2886 ($-\text{CH}_2\text{NH}$), 3350 (NHNH_2); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 4.35 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2$), 4.48 (2H, s, $-\text{NH}_2$), 6.63–7.48 (8H, m, Ar-H) and 7.75 (1H, s, $-\text{NH}$); MS: 271 (M^+), 240, 226, 31.

*N*¹⁰-[(Benzylidene hydrazino)acetyl]-10H-phenothiazine (3):

A mixture of compound 2 (0.25 M) and benzaldehyde (0.25 M) in ethanol (20 mL) with 4–5 drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed on a water bath for about 8 h. The solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure and the solid thus obtained was recrystallised from chloroform-ethanol mixture to get compound 3, yield 72%, m.p. 140–142 °C (Found: N, 10.53; C, 70.03; H, 4.69. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{OSN}_3$: N, 11.69; C, 70.19; H, 4.73%); IR (cm^{-1}): 3032, 1576, 1545, 1472, 870, 735, 707 and 696 (phenothiazine and benzene nuclei), 1548 ($\text{N}=\text{CH}$); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 4.38 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2$), 4.90 (1H, s, $-\text{N}=\text{CH}$), 6.63–7.51 (13H, m, Ar-H) and 7.80 (1H, s, $-\text{NH}$); MS: 433 (M^+), 193, 178.

Likewise other compounds 3b–m were synthesized by treating 2 with various aromatic carbonyls. Characterization data are presented in Table 1.

2-[Benzylmethyl]-3-*N*¹⁰-[(acetylamino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones]-10H-phenothiazine (4a):

A mixture of compound 3a (0.005 M) in methanol (50 mL) and thioglycolic acid (0.005 M) with a pinch of anhydrous ZnCl_2 was refluxed for about 12 h on a water bath. The solid thus obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from methanol-chloroform (5 : 5 v/v) mix-

ture to afford compound 4a, yield 69%, m.p. 160–162 °C (Found: N, 9.15; C, 63.47; H, 4.06. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{S}_2\text{N}_3$: N, 9.72; C, 63.88; H, 4.16%); IR (cm^{-1}): 3033, 1569, 1470, 870, 728, 707 and 695 (phenothiazine and benzene nuclei) and 1710 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ cyclic); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 3.15 (1H, s, $-\text{N}=\text{CH}$), 3.59 (2H, s, $\text{CH}_2\text{-S}$), 4.41 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2$), 6.62–7.49 (13H, m, Ar-H) and 7.82 (1H, s, $-\text{NH}$).

Other compounds 4b–m were synthesized in the similar way using 3b–m. Characterization data are presented in Table 1.

5'-[Benzylidene-2-phenyl-3-*N*¹⁰-[(acetylamino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones]-10H-phenothiazine (5a):

Equimolar solution of 4a (0.001 M) and benzaldehyde (0.001 M) in dioxane (20 mL) in the presence of $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{ONa}$ was refluxed for about 8 h. The solvent was removed *in vacuo*. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol to furnish compound 5a, yield 63%, m.p. 147–149 °C (Found: N, 8.03; C, 68.98; H, 4.31. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_2\text{S}_2\text{N}_3$: N, 8.06; C, 69.06; H, 4.41%); IR (cm^{-1}): 3032, 1570, 1472, 868, 728, 710 and 695 (phenothiazine and benzene nuclei), 1709 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ cyclic) and 1620 ($>\text{C}=\text{CH-Ar}$); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 3.20 (1H, s, $-\text{N}=\text{CH}$), 4.40 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2$), 5.20 (1H, s, $-\text{C}=\text{CH-Ar}$), 6.63–7.52 (18H, m, Ar-H) and 7.70 (1H, s, $-\text{NH}$); MS: 521 (M^+) 281, 266, 253, 237, 204.

Other compounds 5b–m were synthesized similarly from 4b–m. Characterization data are presented in Table 1.

Note

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